

THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE RAMAN OPTOMECHANICAL
STRAIN GAUGE FOR STRAIN MEASUREMENT WITHIN
CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a strain measurement technique for determining the inter-ply strains within a carbon fibre composite laminate. The Raman optomechanical strain gauge has been developed using Raman Spectroscopy and polydiacetylene fibres strained in air or in an epoxy matrix. Polydiacetylene fibres are single crystal fibres, which when excited by particular frequencies of laser light are resonantly Raman enhanced. When under uniaxial strain polydiacetylenes show a linear decrease in Raman frequency, which can be calibrated and used as a strain gauge. These fibres were implanted into carbon fibre composite laminates using a fibre optic as a light guide. The laminates were tested in four-point bending and the in-plane inter-ply strains determined from the resulting spectra. The strains measured from within the laminate have been consistent and repeatable.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre composites are now used as standard load bearing materials in any aircraft design today. With this increased use the testing of these structures has to be carried out accurately and data collection is important. The standard method of strain measurement is via electrical strain gauges attached to the surface of the structure. New methods include the use of fibre optics as a sensing device [1-4] that are either implanted within the laminate or attached to the surface. As strain sensors fibre optics measure distributed strain.

This paper outlines a new technique of measuring strain at a point anywhere within the laminate by using the Raman optomechanical strain gauge. This consists of a polydiacetylene fibre (which is Raman active) and Raman spectroscopy. When laser light of a particular frequency is directed at a polydiacetylene crystal some of the light is scattered inelastically. This is detected as a Raman band at a frequency equal to the vibrational frequency of the molecule. On uniaxial straining the Raman band shifts linearly to a lower frequency and this shift has been calibrated for various types of polydiacetylene fibres [5-7]. To utilise this strain gauge, a polydiacetylene fibre is implanted into the laminate at the point of interest and a fibre optic is used to guide the laser light to and from the implanted fibre.

The particular polydiacetylene chosen was polyDCH which has a strain

dependence of $-19.7\text{cm}^{-1}/\%$ strain, and is stable to temperatures in excess of 200°C . This makes it suitable for implanting into carbon fibre laminates that can reach high temperatures during cure.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Fibre Preparation

The sensor preparation began with the growth of needle like crystals of the diacetylene DCH monomer, 1,6-(N-carbazolyl)-2,4-Hexadiyne (DCH) [8]. These were then polymerised to polyDCH by exposure to 40 Mrads Co γ -rays. The polyDCH fibres were checked under the microscope to ensure there were no visible defects such as cracking, twinning or 'pitting'. Fibres with a diameter of approximately $100\mu\text{m}$ were selected, so as to match the core diameter of the optical fibre, and with lengths of between 8mm and 12mm.

Raman Spectroscopy

The resonance Raman spectra were taken with the output of a 10mW HeNe laser. The Raman microscope (shown in Figure 1, the complete experimental set-up) was used to focus the laser beam on the end of the fibre optic and deliver the 180° back-scattered light to the spectrometer. The spectra were dispersed across a Wright Instruments CCD (charge coupled device) detector to permit rapid and accurate data collection. The 2085cm^{-1} Raman band associated with the vibration of the triple bond on the backbone of the polyDCH was used to measure the fibre strain.

Embedded Fibre Experiments

a) Laminates of dimensions $100\text{mm} \times 25\text{mm} \times 1.016\text{mm}$ were laid up using Ciba-Geigy IM6-6376 and XAS-914c materials. The polyDCH fibre was placed between two 0° plies at 0.381mm from the neutral axis. $100/140\mu\text{m}$ graded index multimode fibre optic was used as the light guide.

Laminates of the following lay-up have been tested:-

- i) $(0,0,\pm 45)_s$, the DCH placed between the 0° plies.
- ii) $(0,0,0,0)_s$, the DCH placed between plies 1 and 2.

Figure 2 shows diagrammatically how the DCH and fibre optic were implanted. The polyDCH fibre was placed along the 0° direction, and the fibre optic butted up perpendicular to it. A small amount of a compatible epoxy adhesive was applied to the joint to 'spot bond' the two components.

Four-point bend experiments were carried out on these laminates to determine the strain dependency, consistency and repeatability of the technique.

b) A sandwich panel of dimensions $330\text{mm} \times 25\text{mm} \times 21\text{mm}$ was constructed of a cross-grain balsa wood core and two carbon fibre laminates of lay-up $(0,0,\pm 45)_s$. This panel was tested in four-point bending to simulate as closely as possible tensile loading.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The theoretical strain shown in the following results has been calculated from simple bend theory using the geometry of the four-point bending tests. As can be seen the theoretical values are approximately double the values measured

experimentally, and this was seen possibly to be due to the effect of :

- a) the length of the implanted polyDCH fibre,
- b) the effect of 'spot bonding' the polyDCH / fibre optic joint,
- c) the possibility that putting the polyDCH fibre into bending caused a reduction of the strain dependence, and
- d) the intrusion of the fibre optic is distorting the strain field around the polyDCH fibre at the exact point that the strain is being measured.

Figure 3 shows the results when four laminates were implanted with varying lengths of polyDCH fibre. The strain dependence remains constant as the length of fibre changes. It has been shown [7] that for polydiacetylene fibres of approximately 100 μ m diameter the stress transfer length is 1mm. As the fibres used are of lengths greater than 8mm the strain is measured outside the region of stress transfer.

Figure 4 shows that spot bonding has no effect on the strain dependence. Laminates were tested where the fibre optic tip had been released, the centre of the polyDCH fibre had been released, and the 'spot bond' was made using an adhesive that would not cure.

The above graphs show that the strain dependence, although lower than the theoretically predicted strain, is consistent and repeatable.

The effects of bending can be seen clearly in Figure 5, which shows the results of the simulation of a tensile test. Even though high strains were not reached the results obtained show that the strain dependence is still lower than theoretically predicted, and equal to that shown above.

Finally, the possibility of the fibre optic affecting the strain dependence is currently under evaluation using finite element analysis. As can be seen in Figures 6a and 6b a resin wedge has built up either side of the fibre optic and the carbon fibres around it are distorted. Using micrographs like the one in Figure 6b the geometry of the laminate can be modelled accurately to determine the strain distribution around the fibre optic. An additional test carried out with the polyDCH fibre and the fibre optic placed in the same configuration on the surface of the laminate show that the measured strain is still lower than the surface strain. As only one laminate has been tested in this way the results indicate that implanting the polyDCH into a carbon fibre laminate does contribute to the lower strain measurements.

CONCLUSION

Although the results show that the strains measured by the Raman optomechanical strain gauge when implanted into a carbon fibre composite laminate, are lower than the theoretically predicted strains, they do exhibit consistency and repeatability. It can therefore be said that the Raman optomechanical strain gauge has been successfully adapted for use in carbon fibre composite laminates.

Figure 1. Experimental Set up

Fig.2. Schematic view of DCH in an 8-ply laminate

Fig. 3. Fibre Length Trials

Fig. 4. To determine the effect of 'spot bonding'

Figure 5. To determine the strain dependence for simulated tensile loading

Figure 6a

Figure 6b. Micrograph showing the implanted fibre optic.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by grants from the Science and Engineering Research Council and British Aerospace plc.

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